

The Influence of Principal's Managerial Skills on Organizational Culture in Public Elementary Schools

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ABSTRACT: Organizational culture has an important role in improving leadership in schools. The problem in this study is that the organizational culture in public elementary schools in Bandar Lampung city is not optimal. The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of the principal's managerial skills on organizational culture in public elementary schools in Bandar Lampung city. This research is a type of quantitative research. The study population amounted to 3359 teachers in public elementary schools in Bandar Lampung City with a research sample of 354 teachers. The research instrument used a questionnaire with a Likert scale. Instrument trials were conducted with validity and reliability tests. The data analysis technique used was simple regression. The results showed that there is a significant relationship between the principal's managerial skills on organizational culture in public elementary schools.

KEYWORDS: Managerial skills, Organizational culture, Principals, Primary schools.

INTRODUCTION

The development of the current era can change the order of educational life to be more qualified. Quality education will not be achieved without being supported by a good school organizational culture. Organizational culture plays a role in determining the direction and purpose of the organization, directing what will be done, and motivating teachers (Jamali et al., 2022). Organizational culture in schools can produce superior and competitive human resources. Organizational culture in each school has different characteristics so that it can be recognized by everyone. The importance of organizational culture in schools has made this term broad to be interpreted in various ways over the years. Robbins et al. (2018) explain that culture is a shared thought developed by a certain group of people that distinguishes it from other groups. This culture is a manifestation of the personality and character of a group of society.

Culture describes a thought process that directs individuals in their behavior in life. So that culture is very sacred and should not be violated by the community group (Szulc, 2023). Culture has its own provisions to always be obeyed, upheld, and followed by the group. Other studies also suggest that culture is a unifier that strengthens community groups that have meaning and direction (Ketprapakorn & Kantabutra, 2022). Organizational culture leads to a productive organization. In addition, it can also improve positive performance for the environment. So that organizational culture is defined as the arrangement of fundamental norms that have been developed by a group when facing internal or external problems (Shaari, 2019). There are seven dimensions of organizational culture developed by Robbins & Judge (2013), namely innovation and risk taking, attention to detail, outcome orientation, people orientation, team orientation, aggressiveness, and stability. While the indicators are being responsible for the risks taken in making decisions, assessing each job in detail, the organization always encourages the achievement of targets, doing individual-oriented work, emphasizing the achievement of school targets rather than personal, how quickly responsive in accepting and completing work, and being comfortable with organizational conditions.

The difference in organizational culture in each school institution is caused by how the principal leads the organization in the school. Principal leadership is one of the important factors in improving school organizational culture. Principals as leaders are obliged to have skills that can support the achievement of an optimal organizational culture. The principal's skills are referred to as managerial skills. Managerial skills are skills that principals have as a strategy to implement management functions effectively and efficiently (Bukhari et al., 2021). Managerial skills have three skills, namely technical, human, and conceptual skills. These three managerial skills are needed to carry out the managerial tasks of school principals with different functions. Technical skills are technical skills or certain expertise regarding knowledge of methods, processes, and procedures to support specific activities (Darwansyah et al.,

2021). Human skills are human skills that are useful for working together effectively, practically, and cooperatively both individually and in groups (Omer & Mkude, 2022). Conceptual skills are skills to provide concepts, ideas, and ideas in the form of plans that are tailored to the real needs in the field (Mugani, 2022).

The three aspects of the principal's skills mean that the principal has a role and responsibility as a leader and manager at school. The duties and responsibilities of the principal as a manager are planning, organizing, implementing, and controlling all activities in the school (Azainil et al., 2021). Furthermore, the indicators of managerial skills are compiling standards and work procedures in detail, being able to use technological devices properly, improving the professional competence of teachers and school staff, creating teamwork between teachers, assessing the performance of teachers and school staff, creating positive relationships with the community, designing educational programs realistically, setting strategies for achieving school goals, making detailed teacher and staff assignments. These indicators are standards for principals to carry out their leadership.

Previous studies state that the managerial skills of school principals have a significant influence on organizational culture (Selfiaty et al., 2021). This shows that good principal managerial skills will affect the formation of organizational culture in schools. Furthermore, research by Syuryana et al. (2023) that there is a significant influence between the principal's managerial skills on organizational culture in public elementary schools in Batanghari Leko District, Musi Banyuasin Regency. Then research by Arif et al. (2019) also shows a significant influence between the principal's managerial skills on organizational culture in public high schools in Medan City. Based on the problems that have been described, there is a gap for researchers that currently there is no research that examines the effect of the principal's managerial skills on organizational culture in public elementary schools.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research is a type of quantitative research that focuses on careful measurement and to answer research questions and hypotheses based on theory (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). This research also includes ex post facto research, which is research on variables whose events have occurred before the research was carried out (Arikunto, 2019). The population in the study was all public elementary school teachers in Bandar Lampung City, totaling 3359 teachers. Furthermore, the sample determination used cluster random sampling technique and obtained 354 teachers. The data collection techniques used in the study were questionnaires and documentation. The research questionnaire uses a Likert scale with five answer criteria, namely Strongly Agree (SS), Agree (S), Neutral (N), Disagree (TS), and Strongly Disagree (STS). The research questionnaire is made based on the dimensions and indicators of each variable. Furthermore, an instrument test was carried out, namely the validity test and reliability test. The validity test uses the Karl Pearson method. Reliability test using Cronbach Alpha. The data analysis prerequisite test in the study consisted of outlier test, normality test, homogeneity test, linearity test, and multicollinearity test.

The data analysis technique used is a simple regression test. Arikunto (2019) states that simple regression is to determine the linear effect between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The following is the general equation of simple linear regression $Y = a + bX$. Simple linear regression analysis in this study was carried out with the help of SPSS 22 software. Furthermore, hypothesis testing was carried out, namely H_0 = variable X partially had no significant effect on Y and H_1 = variable X partially had a significant effect on Y.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results showed that there is a significant influence between principals' managerial skills on organizational culture. The results of the significance test of principals' managerial skills on organizational culture in public primary schools can be seen in Table 1 as follows.

Table 1. Significance test results of principals' managerial skills on organizational culture

Variabel	Std. Error	Beta	Sig.
X on Y	0,032	0,153	0,008

Source: SPSS 22 output

Based on the analysis results in Table 1, it is known that the significance value (sig.) is 0.008, meaning sig. <0.05 then H_0 is rejected. So it can be concluded that the regression equation is significant. The magnitude of the influence of managerial skills on organizational culture is 0.153, which means that the effect of managerial skills on organizational culture partially is 15.3% so that it can be seen in Figure 1 as follows.

Figure 1. The influence of principals' managerial skills on organizational culture in public primary schools

Based on data analysis that has been carried out by researchers, it shows that there is a significant relationship between the principal's managerial skills and organizational culture. Organizational culture is related to the internal and external environment of an organization (Amril et al., 2023). Both environments will affect the people who are in it. The influence that exists in each organization will create its own unique culture that characterizes an organization. This shows that the quality of a good organizational culture will have an impact on improving the managerial skills of school principals.

Managerial skills possessed by school principals can provide innovation to the organizational culture in schools (Lam et al., 2021). The innovation gives positive results to the school environment. The principal is also in addition to being a leader, he is a manager who is an important element in organizational culture. Managerial skills possessed by principals such as technical skills, human skills, and conceptual skills can help organizations increase the capacity and effectiveness of schools for the better (Ye et al., 2022). Human skill means the principal's ability related to how he is able to communicate well and be wise to his members. Technical skill means the principal's ability related to technical ability. This ability includes knowledge and skills in the use of tools and technology that are relevant in the field of education. Then conceptual skill is the principal's ability to provide brilliant ideas and ideas to advance the organization he leads. The three managerial abilities of the principal can be a benchmark for whether the principal can play an active role in the development of organizational culture.

CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

Efforts to create an optimal school organizational culture need support from the principal's leadership as a manager. Based on the results showed that the influence of managerial skills on organizational culture provides a significant effect of 0.008. This means that if the managerial skills variable increases, the organizational culture variable tends to increase. Managerial skills are leadership skills that must be possessed by the principal which consists of three skills, namely technical skills, conceptual skills, and human skills. While organizational culture as a characteristic of an organization that can determine the direction and goals of an organization. Then this research brings practical implications that can be applied by every school in order to improve the organizational culture of the school, namely (1) Managerial skills of principals can be improved continuously because it is proven to improve the organizational culture of the school. (2) The strong organizational culture in the school makes the teachers and other staffs become more motivated and affect the whole behavior of the school community to be good.

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